

D8.1: Initial Dissemination Plan

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3D ICONS is funded by the European Commission's
ICT Policy Support Programme

Revision History

Rev.	Date	Author	Org.	Description
V.01 -draft	21.03.2012	Kate Fernie	MDR	Outline
V.02 -draft	21.05.2012	Kate Fernie	MDR	Additional activities suggested by partners
V.10	09.06.2012	Kate Fernie	MDR	Executive summary added and final edit

Revision: V10 (Final)

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All partners

Statement of originality:

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

3D-ICONS is a project funded under the European Commission's ICT Policy Support Programme, project no. 297194.

The views and opinions expressed in this presentation are the sole responsibility of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission.

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1. Executive summary

This deliverable presents the results of WP8: Dissemination, Task 1 - Dissemination planning and covers months 1 to 24 of the project. The plan presents a dissemination strategy for the 3D-ICONS project and will be updated during the project.

The mission of the 3D-ICONS project is to raise awareness amongst archaeology and architecture content holders of the positive conditions for making content available to Europeana, and to give a persuasive demonstration of best practices to promote use of the project's results by the wider community.

The aims of the dissemination strategy are to raise awareness about the 3D ICONS project and 3D digitisation amongst:

- Internal stakeholders within the partner organisations
- External stakeholders: Organisations with an interest in 3D digitisation including Europeana, cultural heritage institutions, academic institutions, commercial enterprises and others.
- The Research Community
- European Commission's CIP ICT PSP programme: directors, project officers and related projects funded by the programme

The initial objectives of the dissemination strategy are to:

- Define the stakeholder community, identify its interests and the main channels for communication and networking activities;
- Build and extend the contact database by clustering with other projects, participation in events and exploiting the partners' networks of contacts;
- Informing the stakeholder community about news, events and activities by developing a project newsletter, exploiting social networking channels as well as traditional media.
- Providing an up-to-date set of dissemination materials by developing the project website, a brochure and other materials for use by the partners.
- Presenting the project at relevant national and international events

The plan is a live document and will be updated at months 12 and 24 to inform dissemination planning for the year ahead.

2. Dissemination strategy

3D ICONS is co-funded by the European Commission ICT PSP programme started on 1st February 2012 and runs for three years. It brings together partners from across Europe with the relevant expertise to digitise architectural and archaeological monuments and buildings in 3D and is designed to:

- establish a complete pipeline for the production of 3D replicas of archaeological monuments and historic buildings which covers all technical, legal and organisational aspects;
- create 3D models and a range of other materials (images, texts and videos) of a series of internationally important monuments and buildings; and
- contribute content to Europeana using the CARARE aggregation service.

The aim of WP8 (dissemination) is to develop the consortium's strategy for effective dissemination of the project's results in the culture sector business environment and the academic world, its achievements in digitising archaeology/architecture content and preparing 3D models and to raise awareness and transfer knowledge.

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- The Research Community
- European Commission's CIP ICT PSP programme: directors, project officers and related projects funded by the programme

This dissemination strategy has been prepared by MDR Partners. All partners are involved in project dissemination activities.

This initial dissemination strategy for the project aims to:

- Define appropriate **messages** targeted to specific audiences
- Define appropriate **materials** targeted to specific audiences.
- The **timeline** for dissemination activities
- Identify **resources** to be devoted to dissemination activities
- Define partner responsibilities for **tasks**
- Define the information **workflow**
- Establish the Stakeholder **contact database**
- Provide qualitative and quantitative **indicators**

For the initial dissemination plan we have identified 5 main objectives together with the corresponding activities (Table 1):

Objective	Description	2012-13 activity
Objective 1	Defining the stakeholder community	Exploration of the stakeholder community and its interests Identification of channels for networking activities
Objective 2	Building and extending the contact database	Clustering with other projects Participation in events Maximising contacts through the partners' networks to disseminate news
Objective 3	Informing the stakeholder community about news, events and activities	3 issues of the Project Newsletter Use of Mailing lists and Social Networks to disseminate news and drive traffic to the project website Press Notices – project launch
Objective 4	Providing an up-to-date set of dissemination materials	Developing the Project Website to provide a useful information base. Project brochure Introductory powerpoint presentation Project poster
Objective 5	Presenting the project at relevant national and international events	Participation in relevant National/international events International Workshops

Table 1: Dissemination strategy

3. Defining the stakeholder community

Different approaches are appropriate to the different user groups. By developing understanding of the needs and interests of each group, the project aims to make its dissemination activities more relevant to the people and organisations who we hope will be interested in its outcomes once they become available. This awareness will help identify the best channels for contacting stakeholder groups (which email lists, conferences, other means) and in planning dissemination materials and activities, and thus helps raise the visibility of the project.

The 3D-ICONS stakeholder community includes:

- Internal stakeholders in the partner institutions who have an interest or involvement in 3D digitisation and/or the archaeological and architectural heritage;
- UNESCO and cultural institutions with responsibilities for internationally and nationally important monuments and buildings interested in finding new ways of delivering their missions to promote understanding and increase the sustainability of this heritage, and with an interest in tried and tested mechanisms to produce high quality 3D documentation and publish the results online;
- Research community and creative industry SMEs with an interest and involvement in producing high quality 3D documentation of the archaeological and architectural heritage;
- The European Commission and its digital content programmes;
- Europeana, members of the general public, tourists and students who wish to be able to use 3D content to explore and enjoy architectural and archaeological masterpieces.

3.1 Internal stakeholders

Internal stakeholders are one of the target audiences for the 3D ICONS project as it is important to disseminate to policy makers within the partner organisations, to staff or groups within the organisations to be aware of the projects activities and results and to share the news with their contacts.

Staff within the partner institutions may be interested in news about:

- Digitisation of specific monuments and buildings
- The use of particular technologies
- Standards and guidelines
- Releases of new content in Europeana
- Conferences and other events
- Business models

The aim of this dissemination activity is to make the subjects aware about 3D ICONS and its activities and to spread the news to their contacts.

Internal stakeholders will be reached during internal meetings through presentations of the project activities and dissemination of news.

3.2 UNESCO and Cultural institutions

UNESCO and cultural heritage institutions involved in the Europeana Network form an important dissemination target for the project. These are institutions with responsibilities for

the management, protection and understanding of internationally and nationally important monuments and buildings who in many cases also have an interest in using new technologies for documentation and presentation purposes.

Staff within these institutions may be interested in news about:

- Digitisation of specific monuments and buildings
- The technologies and services
- Standards and guidelines
- Releases of new content in Europeana
- Conferences and other events
- Sustainable business models

3D ICONS will interact with this stakeholder community by participating in conferences and events, organising workshops, making use of social channels, by disseminating news and by making materials available on the project website.

3.3 Research community and Creative industry SMEs

This is the community of researchers and creative industry SMEs who are active in the field of 3D documentation of the cultural heritage, and in particular archaeological monuments and historical buildings.

The community is likely to be interested in:

- Specific research outcomes
- The technologies being used and their implementation in specific projects
- Standards and guidelines
- Business models
- Needs and requirements of the cultural heritage institutions
- Participation in conferences and events

3D ICONS will interact with this stakeholder community by participating in conferences and events, organising workshops, making use of social channels, by disseminating news and by making materials available on the project website.

3.4 European Commission

The European Commission is an important stakeholder in the outcomes of the 3D ICONS project and represents both an opportunity to disseminate project outcomes to policy makers and also provides dissemination channels to related projects funded by the programme.

The European Commission, its staff and news channels are likely to be interested in news about:

- Digitisation of specific monuments and buildings
- The results and outcomes of the project
- Delivery of content to Europeana
- Standards and guidelines
- Evaluation of the results

The 3D ICONS project will aim to take advantage of opportunities to present the outcomes at **events** organised by the European Commission spread the word about 3D documentation of cultural heritage sites. The 3D ICONS team will take part in collaboration events organised by the EC to share results with other funded projects. These will be also reached through direct contacts, participation in international events and other dissemination channels (see section **Error! Reference source not found.**).

The project **newsletter** and other news items will be distributed to the project officer via email and twitter.

3D ICONS project will aim to contribute to showing the success of the EC Programmes and initiatives by demonstrating the important progress being made in the direction of accessing, using and sharing cultural heritage resources in ways which adapt to user needs.

4. Identifying the resources

This section identifies the skills and experiences available within the project consortium, and their connections with projects, networks and associations.

4.1 Consortium

The dissemination work package is lead by MDR and which involves all partners in the project consortium with the sole exception of NTUA.

The 3D ICONS consortium consists of 16 partners in 10 countries including Italy, United Kingdom, Greece, Ireland, Spain, Belgium, France, Cyprus and Romania.

All project partners are responsible for contributing to dissemination activities including the identification of events, development of dissemination materials and to the development of the project website. Most of the partners have public relations departments in their institutions, or access to external resources, on which to draw relevant skills and experience for marketing 3D ICONS.

Responsibilities for dissemination activities:

- CISA and MDR together have strategic responsibility for coordinating dissemination activities by all partners.
- MDR is responsible for coordinating the development of the project website and for providing a basic set of dissemination materials.
- KMKG is responsible for coordinating the dissemination of news and information about the project through Twitter, Facebook and the project newsletter
- relevant contacts via the project's stakeholder database
- STARC is responsible for organising a workshop at an international conference during year one of the project
- DISC is responsible for organising a workshop at an international conference during year two
- CISA is responsible for organising a conference during the final year of the project supported by MDR.
- All partners are responsible for disseminating about the project at conferences, events, workshop and via news and social media.
- All partners are responsible for naming a dissemination lead person who will be responsible for reporting on dissemination activities and for contributing to the development of the project dissemination plan, etc.

4.2 Clustering with other projects

3D ICONS has identified a number of projects who are active within its field. These projects represent external networks with resources in place to disseminate news and information with their stakeholders. The strategy for 3D ICONS will be to approach the projects offering to exchange news about project activities and to seek opportunities for collaboration.

The projects which been identified include:

- CARARE¹ (stakeholder community: cultural institutions)
- ASSETS² (stakeholder community: researchers)

¹ <http://www.carare.eu>

- 3D COFORM³ (stakeholder community: researchers)
- Scottish Ten⁴ (stakeholder community: researchers and creative SMEs)
- V-MUST⁵ (stakeholder community: researchers and creative SMEs)
- Europeana⁶ (stakeholder community: cultural institutions)

3D ICONS is a member of the Europeana group of projects and is represented by MDR in the Europeana communications group. The Europeana office maintains the Europeana group website (<http://group.europeana.eu>) and disseminates information about projects, including 3D ICONS, to its stakeholder community through the website, a quarterly newsletter and its news channel. The office also maintains a calendar of events informing group members about upcoming events, inviting participation in clustering activities and disseminating information about project's participation in international conferences and events

The 3D ICONS team will follow the projects identified above via their websites, Twitter and the other social networks.

The aim will be to coordinate the approaches to the projects identified to avoid duplication and to maximum effect. The table below identified which PARTNER will contact specific projects, WHEN contact will be made and WHAT the nature of the contact will be (e.g. to discuss collaboration or partner opportunities, exchange news, etc.).

Project	Partner to contact	When	Nature of the contact
CARARE	MDR	Now	Collaboration
ASSETS	CNRS	Month 3	Exchange news
3D COFORM	CISA	Now	Collaboration
Scottish Ten	Discovery	Month 3	Exchange news
V-MUST	Visual Dimension	Month 3	Collaboration

4.3 Groups and associations

Several 3D ICONS partners are members of groups and associations which are active within the field. These groups and associations each represent external networks with resources in place to disseminate news and information with their stakeholders. The strategy for 3D ICONS will be to explore opportunities to dissemination news and information about project activities with these groups.

² <http://www.assets4europeana.eu/>

³ <http://www.3d-coform.eu/>

⁴ <http://www.scottishten.org/>

⁵ <http://www.v-must.net/>

⁶ <http://pro.europeana.eu>

The groups and associations which have been identified include:

- 3dheritage.org
- Computer Applications in Archaeology (CAA)
- European Association of Archaeologists (EAA)
- Irish Institute of Surveyors (IIS)
- Aerial Archaeology Research Group (AARG)
- European Association of Remote Sensing Laboratories (EARsel)
- Network TechnoHeritage: Red de Ciencia y Tecnología para la Conservación del Patrimonio Cultural (Science and Technology for conservation of Cultural Heritage)

4.4 Stakeholder database

The objective for 2012 will be to build the project's contact database by encouraging subscriptions to the project newsletter, followers on Twitter and membership of the project's Facebook group.

The strategies for building and extending the contact database include clustering with other projects, disseminating news and updates about the project's activities through various channels including direct contacts of partners' network, use of social media, project newsletter, press notices (see section 5) and by participating in conferences and events (see section 7).

5. Informing the stakeholder community

Our objective is to inform the stakeholder community about news, events and project activities. This will be done through the different channels (project newsletter, mailing lists, social networks, press notices) documented below.

Our strategy is to approach the target audience by making use of social media, professional/personal/local contacts from the project partners' network, etc.

Contacts will be made through the use of an appropriate **message** to transmit information which could vary according to the target audience. For example, when reaching the research community we could point out specific academic 3D ICONS publications on the project website or news about forthcoming conferences.

During 2012 the programme of work by partners to capture archaeological and architectural monuments in 3D will be some of the achievements to inform our stakeholder community about.

5.1 Mailing lists

The members of the project team are each registered on various mailing lists for professional reasons. These lists cover different subjects in the Cultural heritage, research and business domains and have different memberships.

The project is creating a document summarising the email lists that each team member will be responsible for circulating project news to. Partners have been asked to identify which email lists team members are signed up to. A master list will then be made and MDR and KMKG will coordinate the dissemination of news items to the lists, with the aim of guaranteeing coverage and avoiding duplication.

The strategy is to post notices about 3D ICONS to the lists (for example the newsletter or a forthcoming event with a link to the project website). Such notices are a good way of driving traffic to the website and allow contacts the opportunity of registering to receive a copy of the Newsletter directly.

The work of sending notices will be done periodically according to the project activities and developments.

The emailing lists which have been identified include:

- HERITAGE
- DIGITAL-CULTURE
- JISC-E-COLLECTIONS
- JISCDIGITALMEDIA
- MUSEUMS-INFO
- MUSEUMINFO-RECORDS
- ARTS-HERITAGE-MARKETING

5.2 Social networks

Twitter

The strategy for **Twitter**⁷ during 2012 will be to:

- Post Tweets related to the project's activities (Newsletter, events, project progresses) or information related to domains of interest to 3D ICONS. This will keep followers informed about the project and activate new discussions around pertinent areas.
- Encourage the partners to share interesting news and then tweet them.
- Monitor events (who's attending what events) and tweet about the event with the event hashtag
- Involve 3D ICONS project members who are active on Twitter to create interest around 3D ICONS by Tweeting about the project and retweeting any tweets of interest.
- Include the project Twitter feed on the home page of the project website.
- Integrate Twitter with LinkedIn and Facebook. Tweets will be automatically re-posted onto LinkedIn and Facebook: this mechanism will ensure a consistent flow of information and will populate the social networks.
- Follow lists of relevant Twitter users. This activity give the 3D ICONS project visibility: some of these users might follow @3DICONS in return or retweet 3D ICONS tweets to their followers etc.

Among the list of relevant Twitter contacts for dissemination we identified:

- @ScottishTen
- @ddsgsa Digital design studio
- @HDSblog
- @Laserscanningeu - Laser scanning Europe
- @lidarnews – Gene Roe
- @UNESCOheritage – UNESCO
- @NottinghamCaves – Nottingham Cave Surveys
- @nextengine – Nextengine

In order to make the best use of Twitter a document containing Guidelines for Tweeting about the 3D ICONS Project has been created (see Appendix I: Twitter Guidelines) and additional useful material on the use of Twitter has been circulated to partners on Basecamp.

LinkedIn

The strategy for **LinkedIn** during 2012 will be to promote discussion about 3D digitisation and about project activities. News posted to Twitter will be republished on LinkedIn. The objective will be to increase the number of followers of the group during the year.

A group has been established for 3D ICONS at:

http://www.linkedin.com/groups?home=&gid=4404844&trk=anet_ug_hm.

Our strategy will be to involve the members in discussions around the project

Among the list of relevant LinkedIn groups for dissemination we identified:

- 3D-COFORM
- 3D Scanning / Reverse Engineering

⁷ <http://www.twitter.com/3Dicons>

- 3D Visualisation and Graphics Programming
- 3D Business
- ArchaeoLandscapes Europe
- Archeology
- CAA: Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology
- CARARE: connecting archaeology and architecture to Europeana
- CIDOC - International Documentation Committee of ICOM
- Computer Vision Technologies
- Digital Heritage Preservation
- Geomatics
- Information Technologies and Cultural Heritage
- Laser Scanning
- Laser Scanning Forum
- The LiDAR Forum
- Open Source LiDAR
- Photogrammetry & Laser Scanning
- Spatial Ireland
- Web3D Professionals
- WebGL Developers

YouTube

A **YouTube** channel has been established for the project. The intention is to use this channel to publish videos about the project and its digitisation activities.

FaceBook

A **Facebook** group has been established for the project at: <http://www.facebook.com/groups/127358380732567/>. This will be linked to the project Twitter feed, with the aim of disseminating news about the project's activities to as wide an audience as possible. Among the list of relevant Facebook pages we identified:

- CARARE
- 3D scanning of Cultural Heritage
- SCUOLA DI ARCHEOLOGIA VIRTUALE V-MUST
- MeshLab

Other media channels

Boletín Proyecto Campus de Excelencia Internacional en Patrimonio Cultural y Natural (Newsletter International Excellence Campus about Cultural and Natural Heritage)

5.3 Press notices

Press notices and press release are an effective way to disseminate the project outcomes to news media: Newspapers or magazines (online or papers versions), news sites, news networks.

A press release will be prepared to announce the start of the project.

6. Dissemination materials

An initial set of dissemination materials has been produced for the project and includes:

Project logo

6.1 Project logo

The project logo was designed by Carol Usher of MDR Partners and approved by the project consortium.

6.2 Project website

The 3D ICONS website (<http://www.3dicons-project.eu/>) was launched in month two month of the project. The aim of this site is to provide information about the project to stakeholders and to related projects, and also to provide an Intranet for members of the project consortium.

The screenshot shows the 3D ICONS website homepage. At the top right, there are 'Register' and 'Login' buttons. The main navigation bar includes 'About', 'News', 'Resources', and 'Community'. Below the navigation bar, there are three image thumbnails: a 3D model of a castle, a 3D model of a landscape with circular features, and a person using a 3D scanner. Below the thumbnails, there are three sections: 'About 3D Icons' with a 'Read More' button, 'Latest News' with a 'See All' button, and 'Twitter' with a 'Follow Us' button. The Twitter section shows a tweet about 3D models of African cultural heritage monuments.

The public part of the website includes:

- About - the project, consortium and activities

- News – news bulletins and newsletter
- Resources – presentations, publications, links and other useful resources
- Community – links to the social networks, gallery and activities calendar
- Contacts

The project Intranet includes:

- Project management – project documents, templates, minutes etc
- Work packages – work in progress, links, etc
- Reviews
- Deliverables
- Dissemination materials

The website is initially made available in English. The project plans to make the public pages of the site available in each of the partner languages.

6.3 Project newsletter

3 issues of the project newsletter will be produced:

- April 2012
- July 2012
- November 2012

The editorial strategy for the project newsletter during 2012 will be to create articles talking about 3D ICONS related topics including:

- project achievements
- events attended by the project Consortium
- partner profiles
- dynamic articles describing activities such as field work
- news from projects active in same area as 3D ICONS (like CARARE and 3D COFORM)

The Newsletters will be created with a summary newsletter distributed to email lists and the full newsletter will be uploaded to the project website. Notices about the newsletter will be posted on the Social networks (Facebook and Twitter) and by project partners to their email lists. The motivation behind publishing a summary version of the newsletter with links to the full articles is to send traffic to the project website.

6.4 Other dissemination materials

A basic set of promotional materials is being prepared and made available for use. These materials include:

- A selection of images made available by project partners for use in dissemination materials
- A project fact sheet and/or brochure
- A 3D ICONS Essentials PowerPoint presentation.
- Templates for fact sheets, presentations etc.

These materials are made available to members of the project for download from the 3D ICONS Intranet. Additional materials will be made available throughout the life of the project as needs are identified by the dissemination plan.

6.5 Acknowledgement of EU funding

Dissemination materials including reports, presentations, promotional material and publications must clearly acknowledge the EU funding through the inclusion of an appropriate statement and the EU flag.

Example: "This project is partially funded under the ICT Policy Support Programme (ICT PSP) as part of the Competitiveness and Innovation Framework Programme by the European Community" (ideally with a link to the ICT PSP website:

http://ec.europa.eu/ict_psp).

Any communication or publication shall state that it reflects only the author's views and that the European Community is not liable for any use that might be made of the information contained therein.

7. Dissemination activities

7.1 Potential national and international events

A series of events have been identified as being relevant to the stakeholder communities targeted by the 3D ICONS dissemination strategy.

CISA will coordinate representation of the project at events to maximise dissemination activity by the partners as far as possible.

7.1.1 Potential international events

Below the list of conferences that are potential venues for dissemination.

Conference	Link	Description	Location	Dates
CAA 2012	http://www.southampton.ac.uk/caa2012/	Annual meeting of the Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology conference.	Southampton, UK	26-30 March 2012
Best Practices in World Heritage Archaeology	http://www.congresopatrimoniomundialmenorca.cime.es/	The First International Conference on Best Practices in World Heritage Archaeology	Menorca, Spain	9-13 April 2012
Museums and the Web 2012 conference,	http://www.museumsontheweb.com/conferences/mw/mw2012	An annual conference exploring the social, cultural, design, technological, economic, and organizational issues of culture, science and heritage on-line	USA	11-14 April 2012
ECLAP 2012	http://www.eclap.eu/drupal/?q=node/65281	Information Technologies for Performing Arts, Media Access and Entertainment	Firenze, Italy	7-9 May 2012
IST Africa 2012	http://www.ist-africa.org/conference2012/	Part of the IST-Africa Initiative, which is supported by the European Commission under the FP7 programme, IST-Africa 2012 is part of an Annual Conference Series which brings together senior representatives from leading commercial, government & research organisations across Africa and from Europe, to bridge the Digital Divide by sharing knowledge, experience, lessons learnt and good practice and discussing policy related	Dar es Salaam, Tanzania	9-11 May 2012

Conference	Link	Description	Location	Dates
		issues.		
Museum Next	http://www.museumnext.org/	The conference will look at three themes, Digital Participation, Digital Marketing and Digital Challenges providing real actionable advice from international museums and leading experts	Barcelona, Spain	23-25 May 2012
Europa Nostra	http://www.europanostra.org/coming-events/190/	European Heritage Congress	Lisbon, Portugal	30 May – 2 June 2012
Virtual Archaeology 2012	http://www.virtualarchaeology.ru	First International Conference on Virtual Archaeology	St Petersburg, Russia	4-6 June, 2012
CIDOC 2012	http://www.cidoc2012.fi/	Annual conference – enriching cultural heritage	Helsinki, Finland	10-14 June 2012
Dimension 3	http://www.dimension3-expo.com/		Paris, France	13-15 June 2012
CCPA/Europeana Network Plenary	Cultural Heritage (European)		Leuven	12-14 June 2012
EDULEARN	http://iated.org/edulearn12/call_for_papers	International Conference on education and New learning Technologies	Barcelona	2-4 July 2012
iCALT 2012	www.scuolaiad.it/ICALT2012/	Annual International Conference on Advanced Learning Technologies and Technology-enhanced Learning	Rome	7-10 July 2012
Digital Humanities 2012	http://www.digitalhumanities.org/dh2012	Conference on computers and humanities	Hamburg, Germany	16-22 July 2012

Conference	Link	Description	Location	Dates
	2cfp			
Web3D conference	http://web3d2012.org/	17 th International conference on Web 3D technology	Los Angeles, USA	5-9 August 2012
Siggraph 2012	http://s2012.siggraph.org/		Los Angeles, USA	5-9 August 2012
EAA 2012	http://www.eaa2012.fi/index	The 18th Annual Meeting of the European Association of Archaeologists.	Helsinki, Finland	29 August – 1 st September 2012
IPRES 2012	http://www.isprs.org/	XXII Congress of the International Society for Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing	Melbourne, Australia	25 August – 1 st September 2012
VSMM 2012	http://www.vsmm2012.org/	The International Conference on Virtual Systems and Multimedia (VSMM) is the premier forum for the presentation of research on 3D acquisition, multimedia visualization, interaction technologies and their applications.	Milan, Italy	2-5 September 2012
ICVRV 2012	http://icvrv2012.csp.escience.cn/	International conference on virtual reality and visualisation	Qinhuangdao, China	September 14-15, 2012
Photokina	http://www.photokina.com/en/photokina/diemesse/index.php	The leading international trade fair for the entire photographic and imaging sector. It is the only event in the world that offers a comprehensive presentation of all the imaging media, imaging technologies and imaging markets – for consumers and professionals alike	Cologne, Germany	18-23 September 2012
EC-Tel 2012	http://ec-tel.eu/	Seventh European Conference on Technology Enhanced Learning	Saarbrücken, Germany	18-21 September 2012

Conference	Link	Description	Location	Dates
EARSeL workshop	http://www.earsel2012.ugent.be/	Advances in Remote Sensing for Archaeology and CH Management	Ghent, Belgium	19-22 September 2012
International Summer School for Cultural Heritage Documentation	http://www.heritage Summerschool.com/home.html	2nd International Summer School for Cultural Heritage Documentation	Seville, Spain	24-28 September 2012
CHiC 2012	http://www.promise-noe.eu/chic-2012/home	The Cultural Heritage in CLEF (CHiC) pilot evaluation lab aims at moving towards a systematic and large-scale evaluation of cultural heritage digital libraries and information access systems	Rome, Italy	17-20 September 2012
VIEW 2012	http://www.viewconference.it/	13 th International Computer Graphics Conference	Turin, Italy	16-19 October 2012
EuroMed 2012	http://www.euromed2012.eu/		Cyprus	29th October - 3rd November 2012.
MCN 2012	http://www.mcn.edu/mcn2012-your-ideas	The annual Museum Computer Network (MCN) conference brought together a community of museum professionals interested in using technology to improve their organizations and enhance the visitor experience	Seattle	07-10 November 2012
Archeovirtual 2012	http://www.vhlab.it/bc.cnr.it/archeovirtual/ http://www.borsaturismo.com/ >		Paestum, Italy	15-18 November 2012

Conference	Link	Description	Location	Dates
Online Educa Berlin 2012,	http://www.online-educa.com/	Technology enhance learning	Berlin, Germany	28-30 November 2012
ICIMT 2012 - 2012 4th International Conference on Information and Multimedia Technology	http://www.icimt.org/cfp.htm	Information and Multimedia Technology	Hong Kong	26-28 December 2012
Museums & the Web 2013	http://www.museumsandtheweb.com/conferences/mw/mw2012	Is an annual conference exploring the social, cultural, design, technological, economic, and organizational issues of culture, science and heritage on-line	USA	c. April 2013
Digital Humanities 2013	http://digitalhumanities.org/conference	Conference on computers and humanities	Digital Humanities 2013	
WAC-7	http://www.worldarchaeologicalcongress.org/	Seventh World Archaeological Congress	Amman, Jordan	January 2013
The American Association of Museums	http://aam-us.org/am/		Baltimore, USA	19-22 May, 2013
ICOM 2013	http://icom.museum/what-we-do/activities/general-conference/		Rio de Janeiro, Brazil	10-17 August 2013
CIPA Symposium	http://cipa.icomos.org/		Strasbourg, France	2-6 September 2013

Conference	Link	Description	Location	Dates
Virtual Retrospect	http://archeovision.cnrs.fr/spip.php?rubrique41	Part of the Federated Cultural Heritage Event	Paris, France	18-23 November 2013

Table 2: Potential international events.

7.1.2 Potential National events

Below the list of potential events where 3D ICONS might be presented on national level.

Conference	Submission Deadline	Link	Description	Location	Dates
EVA Florence	15/3/2012	http://www.eva-florence.it/	EVA Florence is a yearly event offering conferences, workshops, meetings & exhibitions covering electronic imaging, visual arts, and telecommunication initiatives.	Florence, Italy	9-11-May 2012
Heritage Impact	Passed	http://www.ung.org.uk/		Brighton, UK	21-22 June, 2012
ARQUEOLOGICA 2.0	-	http://www.arqueologiavirtual.com/arqueo/	This conference aims to analyze both the present and the future of reconstruction and computer aided render techniques, applied to archaeological heritage and culture.	Seville, Spain	20-22 June 2012
Open Culture 2012	-	http://www.collectionslink.org.uk/about-openculture	Cultural Heritage and Systems providers (UK)	London, UK	26-27 June 2012
EVA London 2012	Passed	http://www.eva-london.org/	Electronic Visualisation and the Arts	London, UK	10-12 July 2012

Table 3: Potential national events.

7.2 Potential Journals

Journal	Link	Description	Deadline	Other
Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage	http://jocch.acm.org/	ACM Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage (JOCCH) publishes papers of significant and lasting value in all areas relating to the innovative use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in support of Cultural Heritage. We encourage the submission of manuscripts that demonstrate innovative use of technology for the discovery, analysis, interpretation and presentation of findings as well as manuscripts that illustrate applications in the Cultural Heritage sector that challenge the computational technologies and suggest new research opportunities in computer science.	No deadline	Special issue on Serious Games – deadline 18 th June
Archeomatica	http://www.archeomatica.it/	A new, multidisciplinary journal, printed in Italy, devoted to the presentation and the dissemination of advanced Methodologies, techniques and emerging technologies for the knowledge, documentation, exploitation and conservation of cultural heritage.	Quarterly	Italian
Journal of Cultural Heritage	http://www.elsevier.com/wps/find/journaldescription.cws_home/620738/description#description	A Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology for Conservation and Awareness. The Journal of Cultural Heritage is devoted to: - Safeguard, Conservation and exploitation of cultural heritage - Analyses and preservation of biodiversity - Sociological and economical analyses - Computer sciences in Cultural heritage	4 issues a year	
Archaeological Prospection	http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/10.1002/%28ISSN%291099-0763	<i>Archaeological Prospection</i> is an interdisciplinary journal, intended to: Inform archaeologists, environmental scientists, site developers, local authorities and regional environmental agencies about the wide range of scientific techniques available for the study of the near-surface environment..	4 issues a year	

International Journal of Heritage in Digital Era	http://www.multi-science.co.uk/ijhde.htm	The International Journal of Heritage in the Digital Era (IJHDE) is a quarterly high quality peer reviewed journal in the area of Digital Cultural Heritage and Digital Libraries.	Quarterly	
Geomatics World Magazine	http://www.vpubs.com/magazine.php?id=1	GW is the leading journal for professional and technically qualified surveyors. GW is published under licence from the RICS.		

Table 4: Potential journals

7.3 3D ICONS international Workshops

STARC will organise a workshop at an international conference during year one of the project to promote the technical results of the project.

DISC will organise a workshop at an international conference during year two of the project to promote the results of the project.

8. Monitoring and evaluation

The dissemination programme will be monitored and evaluated to review:

- what messages (communication of benefits) are going out and who is seeing them
- whether those messages are being understood and remembered, and
- whether the messages are influencing opinions, attitudes and behaviours.

This information will help in planning subsequent phases of the marketing strategy, in developing future marketing activities and to revisions of this marketing strategy plan. It will ensure that the marketing strategy is effectively reaching the target audiences and they are taking action on the messages they receive.

Success indicators:

- Number of international events held
 - Number of attendees
- Number of presentations at relevant conferences
 - Number of attendees
- Number of publications in journal and similar media
- Project website developed
 - Number of hits to website
- Number of 3D ICONS connected social networks
 - Number of members of networks
- Email newsletters produced
 - Number of readers
- Liaisons & agreements with institutions / consortia not involved in project's activities (formal and informal)
 - Number of agreements

Description		Month 12	Month 24	Month 36
International events held	No.	1	1	1
Presentations at international events	No.	10	12	15
Publications	No.	4	6	8
Project website	Visitors	7000	10000	15000
3D ICONS connected social networks	No.	2	3	4
Newsletters	Readers	100	150	300
Liaisons and agreements	No	2	4	6

9. Conclusion

This dissemination plan presents our dissemination strategy for 2012-13 years one and two of the 3D ICONS project.

In the first year of the project dissemination activities will focus on the raising awareness about the project in national and international contexts.

This dissemination plan will be updated by month 24 in preparation for the final year of the project.

10. References

- [1] Annex I – “Description of Work”-DoW

11. Appendix I: Twitter Guidelines

Guidelines for Tweeting About the 3D ICONS Project

KMKG and MDR are managing the Twitter account of the 3D ICONS project (@3DICONS).

The 3D ICONS project members are invited to Tweet about the project or retweet any tweets of interest.

In order to make the best use of Twitter for the Project the following guidelines will be of help:

1. Target audience –The prime focus should be people from Cultural Heritage organisations/institutions. After this, it should be aimed at professionals (not necessary working in the field on Cultural Heritage) and subjects in the field of education. In general, the community we intend to target is Europeana and the digital libraries community, cultural heritage and industry end-user organisations, publishers, online hosts, academic institutions, SMEs.

2. Objectives for Twitter:

- a. Keep key followers informed of 3D ICONS activities (progress made, publications, upcoming events etc.)
- b. Inform followers about topics/issues of interest that are related to 3D ICONS, namely 3D digitisation of the Cultural Heritage.

3. Achieving the objectives:

- a. Informing followers about new content on the 3D ICONS website, Facebook and LinkedIn.
- b. Informing followers about topics/issues of interest that are related to 3D ICONS (i.e upcoming conferences/prizes/info days/calls/research areas/innovations/studies)

4. Tweets posted: Twitter only allows tweets of 140 characters or less, tweets should include a link with a title (to effectively communicate the message) and in some cases use a more confidential tone.

5. 3D ICONS follows – people who are related to the target audience and professionally involved in 3D digitisation. We do not follow people whose tweets are of a personal nature. We will periodically review and 'unfollow' the less useful tweeters to make monitoring the feeds more manageable.

6. Tweeting: it would be useful to Tweet at least once a fortnight

7. Reply: The 3D ICONS account will reply to specific tweets directed at @3DICONS (asking questions or feedback about the project).

3D ICONS Project members (and followers):

- remember to use the hash tag when you are tweeting about the project: #3DICONS
- Please Retweet any tweets that may of interest to your friends and colleagues